

ANALYSIS AND SELECTION OF MONOCHROMATORS FOR A PHOTOTHERMOGENERATOR OF SELECTIVE RADIATION

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Abstract. *This work is devoted to the general description of a photothermogen generator and the solution of one of the problems – the choice of a monochromator with optimal characteristics for use in a selective photothermogen generator. A brief description is given of the structure and principles of operation of the selective radiation photothermogen generator. The technical and economic characteristics of various types of monochromators for use in the structure of a photothermogen generator are analyzed.*

Keywords: *photothermogen generator, selective radiation, emission spectrum, spectral dependence, monochromatization, monochromators, light filters.*

Introduction. It is widely acknowledged that despite many years of research, the issue of increasing the efficiency of converting solar radiation into electrical energy using semiconductor photoconverters (PC) still remains relevant. Much work has been done in this regard, and, of course, the results of these studies have a noticeable positive outcome. However, due to the main reason, the meaning of which lies in the strong spectral dependence of the conversion coefficient on the spectral composition of the incident radiation, the problem has not yet been fully solved. Along with the spectral dependence of the efficiency of the solar cell, there is a problem of the temperature dependence of this parameter. Although the latter is solved by adding additional coolers to the design of solar converters, eliminating the bulkiness of solar energy sources is not only a weight and size problem, but also economically inexpedient.

There is substantial evidence that the creation and implementation of a photothermoelectric converter (PTEC) with a separate load and selected radiation will give a positive result. This work is devoted to the general description of the photothermogen generator and the solution of one of the problems - the selection of a monochromator with optimal characteristics for use in a photothermogen generator [1] of selective radiation.

Statement of the problem. Therefore, several urgent problems have been solved on a global scale, in particular, on the creation of combined hybrid systems. But from the above it follows that methods for eliminating the practically negative effect of temperature on the value of the efficiency of photoelectric converters have not yet been found. Scientific and technical problems associated with the spectral dependence of generation-recombination processes remain unresolved, in particular, the problem of creating tools, methods and technologies for optimal separation of the photoactive part of the light beam and transmission directly to the surface of the photoelectric battery in the photothermogen generator.

Theoretical analysis. In connection with the above, one of the important tasks of technical research work is the selection of a device that allows one to easily isolate the desired range of

spectral radiation, because most of the optical radiation sources in operation, except for some types of lasers, emit a wide range of wavelengths. And the solution to the problem of isolating a narrow-band spectrum is quite complex. Only in the ideal case is it possible to isolate radiation of one wavelength. And, as is known, not all devices can be ideal devices that allow the experimenter to receive light of one wavelength without having some drawbacks.

It has been firmly established that device used to isolate photoactive radiation must satisfy several design, technological, design, and technical and economic conditions. In addition, weight and size characteristics are also important. The reason for presenting such requirements is, firstly, that the selected device is intended to be located in the optical axis between the photodetector and the emitter [2,3]. This means that its location should not be an obstacle in the path of the light beam. Otherwise, the loss of light energy is inevitable. Secondly, the spatial arrangement of the separated light radiations should be so convenient that the placement of both the photoconverter and the thermal converter for the perception of the selected radiation does not seem difficult. Thirdly, the device should not have a complex and expensive design, but should be accessible, simple and inexpensive.

In connection with the above, we will analyze the physics of optical phenomena in some of the most common devices used to distribute the integral light flux into spectra of different wavelengths.

One of the simplest ways to monochromatize a light beam is to pass it through a layer of a substance with selective transparency. They are usually called *filters*. Analysis shows that the use of filters, despite the fact that it is possible to obtain a certain spectrum of light, is unprofitable, because for a selective photothermo-converter with the help of such filters, even if it is possible to select and isolate the appropriate spectrum, the possibility of using the cut-off radiations is excluded. Therefore, in this case, in theory, only one converter should work. This, however, does not give a chance to achieve the set goal.

The use of any additional devices for the purpose of direction only clutters up the entire conversion system. This option is not advisable not only in terms of weight and size indicators, but also from the point of view of economics and technical conditions. In our opinion, filters can be useful only to increase the efficiency of a photoelectric converter selected separately. Then the filter helps to lower the temperature of the solar cell and slightly increases the efficiency of conversion [6].

The next device for distributing the integral light flux is *interference filters*. The transparency region can be narrowed by interference in thin plane-parallel plates. The design of interference filters is as follows: they are glass plates with an area of several square centimeters. One side of the plate is successively covered with a translucent metal film (silver or aluminum), a dielectric film, a second translucent layer of material and is covered with a second glass plate to protect against mechanical damage.

There are *interference-polarizing light filters*. In such filters, layers of optical anisotropic materials are placed between polaroids.

There is a growing consensus that industrial enterprises produce various **light filters**. These include cut-off, narrow-band and band-pass filters for the wavelength range from 0.22 to 25.0 μm . The first of them transmit long-wave radiation and cut it off from the short-wave region of the spectrum.

The most common designs of devices for distributing the light flux into radiation of different wavelengths are *residual-ray monochromators*. The operating principle is based on the

reflection spectra of ionic crystals. In this case, the reflection coefficient is close to 100%. After multiple reflections from plates made of such a material, significant monochromatization of the light beam is obtained.

Among the existing various types of devices intended for our purposes, the most common devices that select the required section of wavelengths from a complex source spectrum are monochromators using dispersion (the dependence of the refractive index on the wavelength) of materials transparent to the corresponding section of the spectrum, from which prisms are made.

It is generally accepted that having analyzed the data of industrial enterprises of several countries, we can see that monochromators of the SF-10 type and others with a quartz prism are currently produced for the ultraviolet range; for the visible range - UM-2 with prisms made of various types of glass; for the infrared range - ZMR-3, IKS12, IKM-1, IKS-21 with prisms made of glass (flint glass F-1 for the range of 0.5-1.7 μm), fluoride lithium (for the range of 0.9-5.5 μm), rock salt (NaCl for the range of 3-15 μm), sylvite (KCl for the range of 9-18 μm), potassium bromide (KBr for the range of 16-25 μm) [4,5].

The next device for separating the light flux is *diffraction monochromators*. In developed designs of spectral devices, the dispersing element is a reflective diffraction grating. For different ranges of the spectrum, appropriate gratings should be selected.

For example, for the visible range, transparent gratings can be used, and for the ultraviolet and infrared ranges, reflective gratings should be used. This is explained by the following: for these areas of the spectrum, there are no materials that are sufficiently transparent and satisfy the technological requirements for cutting grating lines.

In theoretical calculations, the formula is used to determine the distribution of wavelengths in the spectrum given by reflective gratings

$$m\lambda = d(\sin\psi \pm \sin\varphi) \quad (1)$$

where m – is the order of the spectrum, d is the lattice constant, ψ and φ are the angles of incidence and diffraction, respectively.

In the formula, the "+" sign corresponds to the location of the incident and diffracted beams on one side of the normal to the grating, and the "-" sign on the other side. For fixed values of the angle Θ in the device between the incident and diffracted beams (Fig. 3), the formula should be used

$$(2)$$

where, d – device constant;
 β - grating rotation angle.

It should be noted that the relative distribution of light intensity depends on the wavelength, the shape of the line, and the reflection conditions. The first-order spectrum of the echelette is determined by the formula:

$$(3)$$

If the angle Θ corresponds to very small values of the angle ($\Theta \rightarrow 0$), then the parameter $\Delta = 2d\sin(\beta - \alpha)$.

In this case, the radiation diaphragmed in the direction of specular reflection from the working surfaces of the echelette steps has the maximum intensity, and the angle α is called the "shine" angle. In order to reduce the cost of devices such as, for example, SF-4, SF-10, DFS-12, etc., replicas from gratings were used.

Fig. 3. Ray path when reflected from Echelette lines.

The following technology was used to prepare such gratings. The Echelette is covered with a liquid layer of the plate, left to harden, and then removed. The last operation is carried out under pressure. After removal, it is glued to a flat glass plate and covered with a layer of aluminum. The aluminum layer is obtained by spraying aluminum powder (more precisely, by sprinkling) with a spray gun. The optimal size of the glare angle for the gratings is from 10 to 200. In this design, the grating constant depends on the wavelength interval according to formula (3), for which it is intended.

Note that diffraction gratings produce not one, like prisms, but several spectral orders ($m = 1, 2, 3 \dots$ in formula (1)). These spectra overlap. In this regard, to obtain a “clean” spectrum, it is necessary to use preliminary filtration. Preliminary filtration can be carried out by one or several rougher monochromatization methods. As an example, the following can be given. In spectrometers for the near infrared region, in order to separate the spectral orders, it is desirable to use monochromatization using prisms of small dispersion. This method is not applicable in spectrometers for the long-wave infrared region, because there are no transparent materials in sufficient quantities to make prisms.

In technology and industry, there are devices that operate on the basis of the method of double transmission of the decomposed beam through a prism using one collimator lens. And it is called the “autocollimation method”.

Fig. 1. Autocollimation scheme of a prism monochromator.

In these collimators, there are certain dependences of the slit widths on the wavelength. These dependences correspond to several prisms. For example, for the F-1, LiF, NaCl, KCl, K Br

prisms of the IKS-11-12 devices. When conducting experimental studies of the measured value from the wavelength (quantum energy), it is possible to indicate the spectral width of the slit in the most important sections of the spectrum.

Fig. 2. Dependences of the spectral slit width on the wavelength for monochromators IKS-11-12

In order to correctly identify the spectrum inherent in a given effect or substance, in those areas where the measured value and its derivatives with respect to wavelength strongly depend on λ , the spectral slit width must be minimal.

The use of such monochromators is also labor-intensive, because the monochromators of the listed brands themselves have quite large weight and size characteristics. And this drawback is immediately reflected when they are installed in the optical axis. Therefore, when choosing a particular device for dividing the integral beam into spectra of different wavelengths, it is necessary to take this problem into account.

Conclusions. Each photoelectric converter has a certain spectral sensitivity zone and can effectively convert photoactive quanta into electrical energy. There are various designs of radiation monochromators, but most of them have bulky dimensions. The device intended for distributing light radiation should be compact and lightweight - it should not obscure the maximum surface area of photovoltaic and thermoelectric energy converters. The most optimal light distributor is a set consisting of optical lenses and a diffraction grating. It is necessary to develop a special technique for distributing the light flux over different wavelengths and estimating the value of the incident power on the front surfaces of the converters.

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